

The Perceptions of Software Engineers Concerning the Utilization of Bots in the OSS Development Process: An Exploratory Survey

Qualitative Analysis

Danyellias Manso
Informatics Institute
Federal University of Goiás, Brazil
 Goiânia, Goiás
 danyellias@discente.ufg.br

Valdemar Vicente Graciano Neto
Informatics Institute
Federal University of Goiás, Brazil
 Goiânia, Goiás
 valdemarneto@ufg.br

Mohamad Kassab
Boston University (USA)
New York University
 Abu Dhabi (UAE)
 mkassab@bu.edu

I. QUALITATIVE ANALYSIS

The qualitative analysis was performed using questions OQ1 and OQ7. To do so, open coding and axial coding were applied, as mentioned in Subsection C of Section II of the paper. In open coding, the data were meticulously analyzed to create codes related to participants' responses. After the open coding phase, categories were identified, and relationships between codes were established, generating interrelationships. The open coding was conducted using the QualCoder¹ tool, while the graphical representation of the coding was created using Miro².

In the qualitative analysis of OQ1, categories related to perceptions of what constitutes a bot were identified: (i) Automation, (ii) Smart and Autonomous Tools, and (iii) Support and Assistance. Figure 5 provides a detailed breakdown of perceptions related to these categories. It was observed that bots are perceived as automated tools that perform and facilitate specific, often repetitive tasks that would otherwise require human time and effort.

In the qualitative analysis of RQ7, four categories were identified regarding suggested improvements for bots: (i) understanding and contextualization, (ii) reliability and efficiency, (iii) integration and adaptation, and (iv) interface and usability. Figure 6 presents some of the improvements suggested by software engineers within these categories. The analysis revealed that participants recognize the potential of bots to increase efficiency; however, they desire enhancements that improve bots' reliability, situational context, and integration with other tools, as well as a more streamlined and intuitive user experience. These improvements would make bots more adaptable tools, aligned with the specific demands of development.

Fig. 1. Some perceptions related to the definition of a bot

Fig. 2. Some suggestions for improvements related to bots

The analysis of the results obtained from the survey of software engineering professionals, along with the subsequent evaluation, provided insights into professionals' perceptions of bot usage in the software development process and allowed for answering the two research questions, RQ1 and RQ2. Regarding RQ1, it was identified that software engineering professionals perceive bots as essential tools for automation and assistance in software development. They are seen as tools

¹<https://qualcoder.wordpress.com/>

²<https://miro.com/pt/>

that not only accelerate software development but also offer extensive support to professionals, especially when combined with artificial intelligence (AI). On the other hand, for RQ2, it was found that, although bots have a significant impact on the routine of software engineering professionals, they still require numerous improvements to further adapt to their users or collaborators, particularly in terms of understanding and contextualization, reliability and efficiency, integration and adaptability, as well as interface and usability.